

Supplementary material

Table A.1. Median and interquartile range of biomarker observations per patient in the study cohort. Presented in total and stratified by treatment combination and treatment line

	Total					Treatment combination										Treatment line									
						Monotherapy					Combination therapy					First line					Second and later lines				
	N	Median	IQR			N	Median	IQR			N	Median	IQR			N	Median	IQR			N	Median	IQR		
Patients	N*	Range	Q1	Q3	Patients	N*	Range	Q1	Q3	Patients	N*	Range	Q1	Q3	Patients	N*	Range	Q1	Q3	Patients	N*	Range	Q1	Q3	
Total	439				76					362					130					309					
BMI	439	5	12	2	14	71	5	7	2	9	312	2	3	1	4	115	3	5	2	7	268	2	3	1	4
NLR	421	8	18	3	21	72	6	11	4	15	343	6	13	3	16	117	6	14	3	17	298	6	12	3	15
PNI	416	5	11	3	14	72	5	11	2	13	344	6	11	3	14	117	5	12	2	14	299	6	11	3	14
CRP	420	8	15	3	18	72	8	11	3	14	348	7	15	3	18	118	7	13	3	16	302	8	15	3	18
Albumin	421	8	18	3	21	72	8	12	4	16	349	6	14	3	17	118	7	18	3	21	303	6	12	3	15

Abbreviations: IQR, Interquartile range; BMI, Body mass index; NLR, Neutrophile to Lymphocyte Ratio; PNI, Prognostic Nutritional Index; CRP, C Reactive Protein.

*Median number of measurements per patient

Figure A.1. Predicted biomarkers trajectories for a patient with the following characteristics: age 65, male, performance status of 0-1, no comorbidities, and receiving ICIs as monotherapy and as first line of treatment. (A) body mass index (BMI)*, (B) Neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio (NLR)**, (C) Prognostic Nutritional Index (PNI)***, (D) C-Reactive protein (CRP)*** and (E) Albumin***.

A)*

B)**

C)***

D)***

E)***

*. Model with a linear coefficient
 **. Model with a quadratic coefficient
 ***. Model with a cubic coefficient

Figure A.2. Survival process stratified by treatment combination

Figure A.3. Smoothed raw trajectories over time stratified by treatment combination of (A) body mass index (BMI), (B) Neutrophile to lymphocyte ratio (NLR), (C) Prognostic Nutritional Index (PNI), (D) C-Reactive protein (CRP) and (E) Albumin.

Figure A.4. Predicted biomarkers trajectories for a patient with the following characteristics, stratified by treatment combination regimen: age 65, male, performance status of 0-1, no comorbidities, and receiving ICIs as first line of treatment. (A) body mass index (BMI)*, (B) Neutrophile to lymphocyte ratio (NLR)**, (C) Prognostic Nutritional Index (PNI)***, (D) C-Reactive protein (CRP)*** and (E) Albumin***.

A)*

B)*

C)***

D)***

E)***

*. Model with a linear coefficient
 **. Model with a quadratic coefficient
 ***. Model with a cubic coefficient

Figure A.5. Survival process stratified by treatment line

Kaplan-Meier Curve - Stratified by Treatment line

Figure A.6. Smoothed raw trajectories over time stratified by treatment line (A) body mass index (BMI), (B) Neutrophile to lymphocyte ratio (NLR), (C) Prognostic Nutritional Index (PNI), (D) C-Reactive protein (CRP) and (E) Albumin.

A)

B)

C)

D)

E)

Figure A.7. Predicted biomarkers trajectories for a patient with the following characteristics: age 65, male, performance status of 0-1, no comorbidities, and receiving ICIs as monotherapy. (A) body mass index (BMI)*, (B) Neutrophile to lymphocyte ratio (NLR)**, (C) Prognostic Nutritional Index (PNI)***, (D) C-Reactive protein (CRP)*** and (E) Albumin***.

A)*

B)**

C)***

D)***

E)***

*. Model with a linear coefficient
 **. Model with a quadratic coefficient
 ***. Model with a cubic coefficient